

**STAGES OF LEARNING TECHNICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH ON THE
BASIS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES**

Ahmadjonova Shaxnoza Mahamadjon qizi

Named after Islam Karimov

Tashkent State Technical University

Teacher of the Foreign Languages Department:

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Abstrakt: The development of technology and technology of material production, the processes of division of labor, its specialization and cooperation, and ultimately, the entire world economy, culture and language, as a means of human communication, storage and transmission of information, was greatly influenced by three industrial revolutions, which covered more than two hundred years of history.

The first, the Industrial Revolution (PR) (from the last third of the 18th century to the last third of the 19th century), affected a limited number of countries: England (from the last third of the 18th century to the first quarter of the 19th century), France (after the 1789 1794), Germany (from the 40s of the XIX century), the USA (after the civil war of 1861-1865), Russia (only after the abolition of serfdom in 1861), and Japan only by the end of the XIX century. For this reason, the Industrial Revolution was accompanied by the simultaneous expansion of the English technical language into other languages.

Key Words: Transport terminology, Mechanical engineering, Development, Media education, pedagogical level, methodological level, Projects Method, Technology, Way, .

Introduction

The development of technology and technology of material production, the processes of division of labor, its specialization and cooperation, and ultimately, the entire world economy, culture and language, as a means of human communication, storage and transmission of information, was greatly influenced by three industrial revolutions, which covered more than two hundred years of history.

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this reason, the Industrial Revolution was accompanied by the simultaneous expansion of the English technical language into other languages.

In the course of the PR, non-production activities became more complicated - the sphere of providing various kinds of services, including in transport. These are various intermediary services, legal, insurance with an English-language form of presentation and transmission of information, using specific information infrastructures (reference publications, bulletins of the English insurance company "Lloyd", dispatches by "captain's mail", telegraph, etc.). New "transport professions" have appeared: insurance and freight broker, freight forwarder. Perfect command of both English, French and German) was regarded as the main attribute of professional fitness.

The subject of this research is the English transport terminology of the second half of the 20th century, associated with the commercial operation of transport and contractual legal transport documentation.

The research material was about 3000 English transport terms selected by continuous sampling from texts taken from the magazines: " Sea Trade ", " International Containerization ",

The research is based on descriptive and comparative methods. The description of the development of English transport terminology as a system, the study of the features, ways and methods of terminological nomination was carried out on the basis of the existing theoretical provisions in modern terminology , presented in the works of A.A. Reformatsky , V.P. Danilenko , L.L. Kutina , A.V. Superanskaya , B.N. Golovin, R.Yu.Kobrina , V.A.Tatarinova , V.M.Leychika , S.V.Grinova , S.D.Shelova , S.G.Schura , V. V.Feoktistovoy , I.V.Bondarenko and dr. In the English transport vocabulary, there are certain ways of forming transport terms: lexical-semantic, morphological, syntactic. Borrowings play an important role in replenishing the term system . They are important in the formation and development of modern international transport terminology, based on English terms.

In the development of English transport terminology, there is, on the one hand, a striving for the accuracy and completeness of the designation of the concept, which is expressed in the creation of multicomponent terms, terminological phrases, and on the other hand, the desire for brevity, codification of the designation, which leads to the widespread use of abbreviated names.

The structure and content of the thesis. The work consists of an introduction, two chapters, a conclusion, and a list of the main used literature. The introduction substantiates the choice of the topic, determines the relevance and

novelty of the work, formulates the goals and objectives of the research, reveals the theoretical significance and practical value of the work, describes the material and research method. The first chapter discusses the most important issues of terminology in the system of English transport terms, the problem of their standardization. Chapter two is devoted to the study of terms in terms of their classification according to situational and communicative groups that combine new concepts associated with scientific and technological progress in transport. The author examines in stages the course of scientific and technological progress, integration and globalization of international transport and notes the reflection of these processes in the formation of transport terminology. New terms are analyzed in terms of their compliance with the current life requirements of professional activity.

Consequently, in modern terminology, the following can be observed: a constant change in the semantic volume of a term, the emergence of new meanings, a refinement of its material expression, which is a direct consequence of the processes taking place in the world around us. On the other hand, there is the desire of scientists in the most accurate definition of the boundaries of the semantics of the term, in the establishment of the most relevant features of the defined concept. The meaning precisely assigned to the term, its definition determine the term in the scientific sense, determines its corresponding place in the terminology system, makes it the most convenient for operating.

The development of transport terminology as a reflection of the first stage of scientific and technological revolution on the conveyor at the end of 50-60 years of the XX century)

In the middle of the 20th century, a new stage began in the development of the world economy. Many countries, formerly colonial and dependent territories, gained political independence and began to develop the economies of their countries, to join the world economy. The presence at that time of two economic systems - capitalist and socialist - created the basis for powerful rivalry between these systems in various spheres of economic and social relations.

Compared to the pre-war period, the volume of foreign trade has almost doubled.

The solution to this problem was carried out in a short time by the shipbuilding industry due to the serial construction of vessels of increased carrying capacity with a strong hull capable of withstanding stormy conditions at the junction of the Atlantic and Indian oceans ("roaring forties"). Changes in the composition of the fleet, the creation of new transshipment technologies have significantly

expanded the transport vocabulary and made changes in the meanings of many transport terms.

Seaports specially constructed for reception supertankers, became known as "oil» - oil ports , meaning by this term the complex of onshore tanks, tank-terminals (tank terminals) to deep moorings and pipelines - " dzhetis » (jettis), on the bank - installations for the distillation of oil and improving the quality of oil products - " blending " (blending).

An even greater increase in the terminological dictionary occurred in the field of transportation and transshipment of bulk dry cargo ships. This was reflected in the emergence of a general term applied to a ship for the carriage of goods in bulk, i.e. without containers (in bulk) - bulkcarriers , bulkers or in Russian "bulk carriers" and in the appearance of new ones, in addition to the already operated specialized single deck engine ships, vessels for transporting timber - timbercarriers , for transporting ore - p udovozov (ore carriers), coal - uglevozov (coalcarriers), as well as constructs AANII new port of transshipment devices and mechanisms.

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